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АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ СКРИНИНГА РАКА ШЕЙКИ МАТКИ В КАЗАХСТАНЕ

CONTEMPORARY ISSUES OF CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING IN KAZAKHSTAN

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В данной статье рассматривается проблема нехватки высококвалифицированных цитологов в интерпретации цитогамм, в том числе, наличия методологических ошибок как неправильного или некачественного взятия мазков, которое приводит к возникновению и упущению рака. Отмечено, что несмотря на обширно распространенные скрининговые программы по всему миру, рак шейки матки (РШМ) в течение многих лет продолжает оставаться в центре внимания. РШМ определен как онкозаболевание, которое можно предотвратить благодаря усовершенствованной программе

скрининга. Проанализированы существующие в настоящее время в нашей стране нормативные документы и выявлено, что они не дают однозначных ответов на вопросы, касающиеся возраста начала проведения скрининга РШМ и временного интервала между тестами, отсутствует четкая схема программы организованного цитологического исследования скрининга РШМ. В результате сделан вывод, что с точки зрения клинической оценки, цервикальная цитология относительно нечувствительна для выявления предраковых состояний и начального РШМ и должна часто повторяться, для того чтобы достичь запланированной эффективности.

This article discusses the problem of the lack of highly qualified cytologists in the interpretation of cytograms, including the presence of methodological errors as incorrect or poor-quality smear taking, which leads to the occurrence and omission of cancer. It is noted that despite the widespread screening programs around the world, cervical cancer (cervical cancer) continues to be in the spotlight for many years. Breast cancer is defined as a cancer that can be prevented thanks to an improved screening program. The regulatory documents currently existing in our country have been analyzed and it has been revealed that they do not provide unambiguous answers to questions concerning the age of the beginning of the screening of breast cancer and the time interval between tests, there is no clear scheme of the program of organized cytological examination of breast cancer screening. As a result, it was concluded that from the point of view of clinical evaluation, cervical cytology is relatively insensitive for the detection of precancerous conditions and initial breast cancer and should be repeated frequently in order to achieve the planned effectiveness.

Ключевые слова: рак шейки матки, скрининг, цитологический метод, ВПЧ, вакцинация, кольпоскопическое исследование.

Key words: cervical cancer, screening, cytological method, HPV, vaccination, colposcopic examination.

Introduction. Cervical cancer (CC) remains the fourth most common cancer in developing countries and is the leading cause of death among women aged 15-44, despite widespread screening programs around the world. It is the only cancer that can be prevented by an improved screening program. An estimated 604,000 cases of cervical cancer were diagnosed worldwide in 2020 and about **342, 000** women died from the disease [1]. Currently, the current screening program of the Republic of Kazakhstan for cervical cancer is carried out at the age of 30-70 years, who are not under dynamic observation with malignant neoplasms of the cervix 1 time in 4 years [2; 4]. This program has its drawbacks regarding the lack of a clear algorithm for obtaining screening results, the late start of screening at the age of 30 years and the lack of other diagnostic indicators with the exception of oncocytology.

Cervical cancer (CC) is a malignant tumor originating from the mucous membrane of the cervix. The etiology of cervical cancer is sporadic. The development of this disease is not associated with the presence of known hereditary syndromes. The cause of cervical cancer is HPV. There are more than 100 oncogenic HPV subtypes 16, 18, 31, 33, 35, 39, 45, 51, 52, 56, 58, 59 and more, among which the 16 and 18 subtypes have a high carcinogenic risk [4-6]. In countries with a high incidence of cervical cancer, persistent HPV occurs in 10-20% of women, while in countries with a low incidence – only 5-10%. As risk factors for the development of this pathology, the following are considered: early onset of sexual activity and early first birth, frequent change of sexual partners, refusal of "barrier" type contraceptives, smoking, use of oral contraceptives, immunosuppressant, as well as the influence of various sexually transmitted infections [7].

Each year, 604 000 new cases and 342 000 deaths from cervical cancer are registered worldwide in 2020 [1]. CC is an important health problem in developing countries. Most women are registered already with a progressive course of the disease. Probably, this phenomenon is associated with the low level of women's knowledge and low priority in relation to their own health [1]. For

example, Sub-Saharan Africa is the region with the highest incidence of cervical cancer in the world and a correspondingly high mortality rate among women.

According to statistics, in 2021 36,127 new cases of malignant neoplasms were registered in Kazakhstan, 20,727 (57.4%) of which were women. In 2020, 13676 deaths, 6496 (47.5%) of which are women. 70% of these are workable population, 15.4% of women with malignant neoplasms died in reproductive age [8].

The progress of cervical cancer is a sequential process, characterized by corresponding changes in the cytological and histological picture for each stage. As a result of infection of the epithelium of the cervix, usually carried out sexually, HPV may be present in 10-15% of the young population [1]. Following infection, full copies of the virus are found in the episomes of the host cell. Here the virus completes its life cycle and in many cases produces a transient infection that does not cause any significant cytological changes. In non-oncogenic HPV infections, the virus disappears on average within 6-9 months. However, whole virus particles can cause low-grade damage to the squamous epithelium of the cervix. These damaged cells, detected by PAP analysis of smears from the cervical epithelium followed by a biopsy, are classified as intraepithelial lesions, which corresponds to grade I (low) dysplasia (CIN1). At this stage, the risk of developing subsequent damage and transition to a more severe degree of dysplasia is small. However, in some patients, HPV integrates its own DNA into the host cell's genome, resulting in high-grade dysplasia. Lesions corresponding to the I (low) degree of dysplasia and including the DNA of high-risk oncogenic HPV have the potential to progress to medium (CIN2) and high (CIN3) degrees of dysplasia. This can happen if there is no treatment for 6-24 months. CIN3 acts as the last harbinger of cancer, according to some data, it can develop on average for about 10 years, successively passing to the II degree, then to the III degree of dysplasia. The emergence and development of CIN3 requires sustained HPV infection of high oncogenic risk. It should be noted that in countries where a high prevalence of cervical cancer, the main obstacle is for early detection of this disease is the lack of effective preventive screening programs [9].

According to AOE, the criterion confirming the accuracy of the screening test for the detection of CIN3 indicates the presence of precancerous changes, since the vast majority of women with a similar pathology who were not treated, were diagnosed with invasive cervical cancer. Taking into account the peculiarities of cervical carcinogenesis and the relative rarity of cervical cancer cases among women who are regularly examined can count on a positive outcome of treatment and observation in a controlled clinical setting. At the same time, CIN2 does not indicate a mandatory transition to a malignant form, since it includes some precancerous changes characteristic of CIN3, and some changes characteristic of CIN1 (the latter regress on their own). Although CIN2 indicates the need for treatment, the American Society for Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology recommends that detection of CIN2 should not be the primary goal of screening for cervical cancer [9; 10].

Ideally, the intervals between screenings by different methods should be timed so that invasive cancer could not develop until the next screening. Due to the fact that there are few studies containing sufficient data on cancer that could directly establish the risk of its development, CIN3 must be considered as an indicator of a very high risk of developing cervical cancer [9].

Most cases of PVI infection and many cases of CIN1 and CIN2 development are transient and do not progress to CIN3 and cervical cancer. Potential harms associated with the discovery of these transient pathologies include the anxiety associated with a positive result after undergoing cancer screening. Psychological pressure associated with the detection of a sexually transmitted disease, discomfort from additional diagnostic and therapeutic procedures, the appearance of bleeding during treatment and, in the long term, a high likelihood of pregnancy-related complications such as preterm labor provoked by treatment. A positive screening test result at any age may be associated with an increased risk of developing cancer and lead to a desire to have more screenings, often with fear of repeating a positive result [9].

Until now, the PAP test (or cytological method) has a number of significant limitations. In terms of clinical assessment, "cervical cytology is relatively insensitive for detecting precancerous conditions and initial cervical cancer and must be repeated frequently to achieve the intended efficacy." The researcher's mistake lies in the interpretation of cytograms and requires a highly skilled cytologist. Also, methodological errors such as incorrect or poor quality smears can lead to false negative or indeterminate results. The cytological method provides information about the state of the cervix only at the time of the study, however the active forms of cancer may develop in the intervals between screening rounds. Cytological results should include borderline or questionable features to achieve high sensitivity, which generate an unnecessarily high percentage of patients referred for biopsy and treatment. In the domestic literature, there are more and more reports of the low effectiveness of PAP smears, in which the cytological method does not justify itself and does not lead to a significant reduction in mortality and morbidity from cancer [10].

However, despite the above shortcomings, the cytological method is still the main laboratory element of screening programs. In the last 30 years, a number of insurmountable obstacles to its prospective advancement have arisen. First of all, we have in mind the emergence of new cytological criteria for evaluating a smear (the Bethesda system), the need to train specialists for an intermediate assessment - laboratory technologists, and the catastrophic shortage of highly qualified doctors - cytologists. The quality of the cytological analysis largely depends on the experience and qualifications of the staff. All cervical cancer screening guidelines from the US National Academy of Medicine, the US Preventive Services Task Force, the American Society for Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology (ASCCP), the American Cancer Society, and the American Society for Clinical Pathology have been aligned. Recommendations include screening women aged 21 to 65 with a Pap test every 3 years. For women aged 30 to 65 years, a combined Pap and HPV test every 5 years is recommended as an alternative to a Pap test every 3 years. HPV co-testing is not recommended for women under 30 years of age. The Pap test should be repeated after 2-4 months if the initial data are unsatisfactory. If combined testing results in a negative Pap test and a positive HPV test, then both tests should be repeated after 12 months.

In Kazakhstan, until 2018, the target group was women aged 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60 who were not registered with cervical cancer. Since 2018, screening has been carried out in women aged 30-70 years who are not registered with the dispensary for cervical cancer [2]. The stage of screening for early detection of cervical cancer includes: 1) a cytological examination of a smear from the cervix with Papanicolaou stain (Pap test), which is carried out by the traditional method or using the method of liquid cytology with interpretation according to the Bethesda Terminological System (BTS), 2001; 2) in-depth diagnostics (colposcopy, biopsy, histological examination) with cytological conclusions on TSB [2].

Table 1. Identification of cervical cancer for 3 years in the Karaganda region

Year	Total detected cervical cancer	CC was detected in the multidisciplinary hospital № 3 of screening age	CC detected by screening	I stage	II stage	III stage	IV stage
2019	152	130(86%)	22(14%)	13(60%)	6(27%)	3(13%)	
2020	142	115(81%)	27(19%)	16(59%)	8(29%)	3(12%)	
2021	165	131(80%)	34(20.0%)	19(55%)	10(29%)	5(16%)	

The above table (Table 1) was prepared based on the data of the Cancer Patient Registry from 2019 to 2021. In the Karaganda region, 71643 women were examined for early detection of precancerous and neoplastic conditions of the cervix, 459 patients were identified. In 2021, 165 cases of cervical cancer were detected, which is 23 cases more compared to 2019. In 2019, the share of new-

ly diagnosed cases of cervical cancer in the framework of the screening program was 14%. After 2 years, in 2021, the share increased by 6.0%, amounting to 20% [2; 8].

The survey consisted of 5 questions that touched on the awareness of cervical cancer among the female population from 18 to 50 years old in the amount of 200 people in the city of Karaganda. The purpose of the survey was to identify weaknesses in screening in general. Survey participants had the opportunity to make suggestions for its improvement.

According to the data, the first question was asked in order to inquire about the women's gynecological history, the first group 55% of the women answered that they had no gynecological disease. The second group 36% women answered that they had a gynecological disease, but did not indicate the diagnosis. Only the third group 3% of them answered that they did not know (pic. 1).

Picture 1. Answers to the question 1.

To the second question, 54% of women answered that they were screened, 46% answered that they weren't (pic. 2).

Picture 2. Answers to the question 2.

To the third question: what is the frequency of visiting a gynecologist, 37% answered that they do not remember, 35% every year, 28% answered every half a year. Almost half of the women surveyed do not know about the last date of visiting a gynecologist, which indicates a weak work of awareness and the importance of visiting a gynecologist every six months (pic. 3).

The fourth question: conversance of cervical cancer showed that 70% of women informed about cervical cancer, which shows a good trend for early detection of cancer. 19% answered that had no information, 11% chose the option I find it difficult to answer (pic. 4).

Picture 3. Answers to the question 3.

Picture 4. Answers to the question 4.

Picture 5. Answers to the question about vaccination.

41% answered positively about vaccination, 30% found it difficult to answer and 28% answered no (pic. 5).

Prevention of cervical cancer should be primary HPV prevention by vaccination of girls 9-14 years old and women 15-20 years old. Also, information prevention about health, warning about the use of tobacco, alcohol. Sexual education should be covered with taking into account the age and culture sensitive.

Secondary prevention screening for women over 30 includes testing for high-risk HPV.

Tertiary prevention treatment of invasive cancer at any age.

Vaccination against HPV is a recognized method of preventing papillomavirus infection and HPV-associated diseases, including cervical cancer.

Mass vaccination is supported by WHO, ACOG, ESGO, SGO, ACS and many other organizations. This is an essential component of the WHO global strategy to accelerate the elimination of cervical cancer as a public health problem.

WHO recommends that at least 90% of girls under the age of 15 to be vaccinated against HPV by 2030. This, along with screening and early treatment, should reduce new cases of cervical cancer by 42% by 2045 and avert 14 million deaths by 2070 [1; 8; 9].

Conclusion. CC is a visual form of the disease, so the possibilities of its early detection are practically unlimited. For this, the correct use of available and informative methods of morphological and endoscopic diagnostics is sufficient. In addition, timely detection and treatment of background and precancerous processes of the cervix can prevent the development of cervical cancer. And also at the moment, 3 types of vaccines against human papillomavirus are available on the international market, which are effective against different numbers of strains of human papillomavirus. These vaccines are intended for intramuscular use, the vaccination course consists of two or three doses of the drug, depending on age.

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